

A New Parallel Integer Factorization Algorithm based on Simple Continued Fraction Expansion of \sqrt{N}

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Abstract

The problem of factoring large integers has now become of crucial importance for applied mathematics, particularly for applications in cryptography. The discovery of any new algorithm in this area could cause a significant impact to the traffic of information, encrypted by RSA cryptography. Therefore, a proposal for a new algorithm needs to be evaluated by the scientific community, so that the appropriate security recommendations can be made. Many factoring methods rely on search for the pair $(x, y) \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $x^2 \equiv y^2 \pmod{N}$ and $\gcd(xy, N) = 1$. This article describes a new method to search these numbers through a pattern of repetition of residues, when we perform the simple continued fractions expansion of \sqrt{N} .

Keywords: RSA cryptography, Integer factorization, Continued Fraction, Parallel

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1. Introduction

Integer factorization is a fundamental problem in number theory and plays a crucial role in the security of cryptographic systems, such as RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman). RSA relies on the difficulty of factoring the product of two large prime numbers, known as the modulus $N = p \times q$. The security of RSA is based on the fact that while multiplying two prime numbers is computationally efficient, the inverse operation—factoring N into its constituent primes—is considered intractable for sufficiently large instances using known classical methods [2].

The complexity of integer factorization has been extensively studied, and various algorithms have been proposed, such as trial division, Fermat's method, the quadratic sieve, and the elliptic curve factorization method [4]. However, these methods have subexponential complexity, making the factorization of numbers with hundreds of digits impractical with current technology. The threat of quantum algorithms, such as Shor's algorithm [5], which can factor integers in polynomial time, poses a future challenge to the security of RSA.

One of the most well-known methods in this category is the Continued Fraction Factorization Algorithm (CFRAC), proposed by Morrison and Brillhart in 1975 [1][3]. This algorithm uses the continued fraction expansion of the \sqrt{N} , where N is the number to be factored. This expansion generates a sequence of rational approximations $\frac{P_k}{Q_k}$, such that Q_k and P_k that satisfy the relation: $P_k^2 \equiv Q_k \cdot (-1)^k \pmod{N}$. The approximations are used to generate congruences of the form $x^2 \equiv y^2 \pmod{N}$ where x and y are integers. These congruences are obtained from linear combinations of smooth relations (numbers whose prime factors are small). Once a valid congruence is found, the greatest common divisor (GCD) between $(x - y)(x + y)$ and N is computed, which may reveal a non-trivial factor of N . The main limitation of CFRAC is its reliance on the factorization of smooth numbers, which makes the algorithm less efficient for very large numbers. Additionally, the need to store and process a large number of relations makes it impractical for large-scale instances.

The new approach I am proposing circumvents this need for factoring the residuals, reconstituting congruence $x^2 \equiv y^2 \pmod{N}$ by searching for equal residuals as will be described below.

2. Method

We starting looking for solution of following quadratic Diophantine equation:

$$x^2 - u^2 - D(y^2 - v^2) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where D is a integer composite number, and $(x, y, u, v, D) \in \mathbb{Z}$ are

it solutions. Therefore:

$$x^2 - u^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{D} \quad (2)$$

If $x \not\equiv \pm u \pmod{D}$ then $1 < \gcd(x + u, D) < D$ and $1 < \gcd(x - u, D) < D$ are distincts factors of D .

We must find solutions to the equation 1 for which we do not need to factor D . There are many methods to solve We propose split a original equation in two parts:

$$x^2 - Dy^2 - (u^2 - Dv^2) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Each parts are a same general Pell's Equation:

$$Z = A^2 - DB^2 \quad (4)$$

When we find equal values of Z for distincts values of A and B , we solve the original equation.

2.1. Exemple

Given a number $D = 7 * 13 = 91$, the equation 1 has as solution $(x, y, u, v) = (124, 13, 19, 2)$ since $124^2 - 91 * 13^2 = 19^2 - 91 * 2^2 = -3$. So, we perform the test $\pmod{(124 - 19, 91)} = 14 \neq 0$ and $\pmod{(124 + 19, 91)} = 52 \neq 0$, In this case $\gcd(124 - 19, 91) = 7$ and $\gcd(124 + 19, 91) = 13$ are both prime factors of 91. The same method is can be applied for another solution $(x, y, u, v) = (10, 1, 725, 76)$.

There are two different domains of solutions for the equation. Values for which $|Z| < \sqrt{D}$ and $|Z| > \sqrt{D}$. I choose to use an algorithm for the first one, due to the simplicity of implementation and computational cost. However, both solutions are acceptable for the problem. For the case $|Z| < \sqrt{D}$ it can be shown that all solutions are convergent of the continued fraction expansion of \sqrt{D} .

2.2. Simple continued fraction Algorithm

Given a non-perfect square integer number D , \sqrt{D} can be expressed by:

$$\sqrt{D} = q_0 + \frac{1}{q_1 + \frac{1}{q_2 + \frac{1}{q_3 + \dots}}} \quad (5)$$

In synthetic notation we can write

$$\sqrt{D} = [q_0; \overline{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{l-1}, 2q_0}] \quad (6)$$

where $l = l(\sqrt{D})$ is the length of the period and $q_0 = \lfloor \sqrt{D} \rfloor$ (floor function), and q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{l-1} are the quotients of the expansion and the slash indicates that they repeat like a palindrome.

The convergent of order j for $j > 0$ is given by:

$$\frac{A_j}{B_j} = [q_0; q_1, q_2, \dots, q_j] \quad (7)$$

where

$$A_j = q_j A_{j-1} + A_{j-2} \quad (8)$$

and

$$B_j = q_j B_{j-1} + B_{j-2} \quad (9)$$

where $A_{-2} = 0, A_{-1} = 1, B_{-2} = 1, B_{-1} = 0$. The complete list of quotients q_j is given by the following procedure: Setting $d = \lfloor \sqrt{D} \rfloor$ and $P_0 = 0$ and $Q_0 = 1$ for $j \geq 0$ we have:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{j+1} &= q_j Q_j - P_j \\ Q_{j+1} &= \frac{D - P_{j+1}^2}{Q_j} \\ q_{j+1} &= \left\lfloor \frac{P_{j+1} + d}{Q_{j+1}} \right\rfloor \end{aligned}$$

The convergent A_j, B_j and the residuals Q_j are related as follows way:

$$A_{j-1}^2 - DB_{j-1}^2 = (-1)^j Q_j \quad (10)$$

The convergent A_j, B_j assume larger values the larger j is. However, for practical purposes of our algorithm, we do not need to deal with the total values, but rather the residues of A_j modulo D .

For this algorithm, only simple arithmetic operations are performed, so the computational complexity is linked to the algorithm used for the multiplication of large integers, as well as a robust calculation of the integer part of \sqrt{D} .

The objective is to produce four lists of numbers that will be used to generate the parallelization, $\zeta_i = [(-1)^i Q_i, P_i, A_i, A_{i-1}]$. The first two elements of this quadruple have a size of $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{D})$ and the last two $\mathcal{O}(D)$.

This calculation needs to be iterative, but it is not necessary to produce a very large list, which does not impact the total computational time.

2.3. Algorithm II - Large-Step Algorithm

This step consists of, from two distinct quadruples ζ_i and ζ_j such that $\gcd(Q_i, Q_j) = 1$, obtaining a third $\zeta_k = [(-1)^k Q_k, P_k, A_k, A_{k-1}]$ such that $Q_k < \sqrt{D}$ and $k \approx i + j$. Algorithm Summary:

1. Find the multiplicative inverse M of $Q'_0 = Q_i Q_j$

$$MQ'_0 \equiv 1 \pmod{D} \quad (11)$$

2. Solve the linear Diophantine equation:

$$XQ_i + YQ_j = P_j - P_i \quad (12)$$

and assume $P'_0 = P_i - XQ_i$ where $0 < P'_0 < Q'_0$

3. Use Algorithm I to perform the continued fraction expansion of $q'_0 = (P'_0 + \sqrt{D})/Q'_0$ with A'_{-2} and A'_{-1} initialized to 1 and 0 respectively. Adopt the stopping criterion $0 < Q'_m \leq \sqrt{D}$
4. Put $Q'_k = Q'_m, T'_k = P'_m$,

$$F_{k-1} \equiv MA_{i-1}A_{j-1}(P'_m A'_{m-1} + Q'_m A'_{m-2}) \pmod{D}, \quad (13)$$

$$F_k \equiv MA_{i-1}A_{j-1}(P'_{m+1} A'_{m+1} + Q'_{m+1} A'_{m-1}) \pmod{D}. \quad (14)$$

If $F_{k-1} \equiv Q_k \pmod{D}$ then $(-1)^k = 1$ otherwise $(-1)^k = -1$. Thus we have a new quadruple $\zeta_k = [(-1)^k Q_k, T_k, F_k, F_{k-1}]$

With this procedure we can generate a list of widely spaced quadruples, which will be used to parallelize the iterative production of other quadruples.

During execution, the most computationally complex step would be the solution of the linear Diophantine equation, which involves calculating the greatest common divisor. In less robust implementations, it is possible to show that the complexity of this algorithm is $\mathcal{O} \log_\phi \min(A, B)$ where $\phi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$ and A, B represent the number of digits in the numbers. This step can be done in parallel, which can provide a significant gain if the total number of processes to be distributed is large.

2.4. Algorithm III - Forward or Backward Single-Step Algorithm

In this step we start from a quadruple ζ_i , we calculate the next ζ_{i+1} or previous ζ_{i-1} .

1. Given a quadruple $\zeta_k = [(-1)^k Q_k, P_k, A_k, A_{k-1}]$, where $T_k \equiv P_k \pmod{Q_k}$ and $q = \lfloor (T_k + d)/Q_k \rfloor$ we calculate:

$$P_{k+1} = qQ_k - T_k, \quad q_k = q + \lfloor (d - T_k)/Q_k \rfloor, \quad Q_{k+1} = (D - P_{k+1}^2)/Q_k \quad (15)$$

or

$$P_k = q_k Q_k - P_{k+1}, \quad Q_{k-1} = (D - P_k^2)/Q_k \quad (16)$$

Let s_k and t_k be integers such that $s_k^2 = t_k^2 = 1$, we define:

$$\zeta_k^F = [(-1)^{k+1} Q_{k+1}, P_{k+1}, s_k A_k \pmod{D}, s_k A_{k-1} \pmod{D}] \quad (17)$$

or

$$\zeta_k^B = [(-1)^{k-1} Q_{k-1}, P_k, -t_k A_{k-2} \pmod{D}, t_k A_{k-1} \pmod{D}] \quad (18)$$

2. Let $S = [X, Y, Z, W]$ be a quadruple. Compute $q = \lfloor (Y+d)/|X| \rfloor$ and

$$Y' = q|X| - Y, \quad X' = (Y'^2 - D)/X \quad (19)$$

$$Z' = qZ + W, \quad W' = Z \quad (20)$$

e $S' = [X', Y', Z', W']$. If $S = \zeta_k^F$ then $S' = \zeta_{k+1}^F$ with $s_{k+1} = s_k$; if $S = \zeta_k^B$ then $S' = \zeta_{k-1}^B$ with $t_{k-1} = -t_k$

Since the input is just a quadruple, we can execute this procedure on as many processors as we have available. To execute the factorization algorithm we do not need to retain the entire quadruple in memory, but only the first and fourth elements $[(-1)^i Q_i, A_{i-1}]$ and apply the verification algorithm.

2.5. Algorithm IV - Parallelization

The objective of this step is to build a list of quadruples conveniently spaced by the residue spectrum in order to find equal values.

1. With algorithm I produce a list with i quadruples;
2. search for the largest element $j < i$ for which $\gcd(Q_i, Q_j) = 1$;
3. With algorithm II calculate the quadruple $\zeta_k = LS(\zeta_i, \zeta_j)$ where we have $k \approx i + j$;
4. Use algorithm III to generate a list of quadruples from ζ_k
5. Repeat the procedure from the second step until the desired value is reached.

Since we have the relation $k \approx i + j$ where we have, at most, $j = i - 2$ we can say that this sequence grows limited by the Fibonacci sequence, therefore the number of steps to calculate a quadruple in position s is of the order of $\mathcal{O}(\log_\phi s)$

2.6. Algorithm V - Check solution

All the pairs calculated in the previous algorithms are accumulated each in a hash table with the same key. When we verify a real collision for the elements Q or $(-1)^i Q_i = (-1)^j Q_j$ we perform the following procedure:

If $A_{i-1} \neq \pm A_{j-1} \pmod{D}$ then:

$$p_1 = \gcd(A_{i-1} - A_{j-1}, D) \tag{21}$$

156 and

$$p_2 = \gcd(A_{i-1} + A_{j-1}, D) \tag{22}$$

157 are non-trivial prime factors of D.

3. Application examples

3.1. Case in which all coincidences are fortuitous

159 Let us consider the number $D = 43 * 71 = 3053$ Since it is a small
 160 number we do not need to resort to the large stride algorithm and we
 161 only use the first one.
 162

i	P_i	Q_i	A_i
-2	-	-	0
-1	-	55	1
0	0	1	55
1	55	-28	166
2	29	79	221
3	50	-7	428
4	55	4	2618
5	53	-61	3046
6	8	49	2611
7	41	-28	1720
8	43	43	2998
9	43	-28	1555
10	41	49	1500
11	8	-61	2
12	53	4	1554
13	55	-7	1941
14	50	79	442
15	29	-28	214
16	55	1	0

164 When observing the elements of the third column corresponding
 165 to the residues Q_i we see that the indices 1 and 7 are equal, as are
 166 2 and 14. In these cases we perform the algorithm V test to verify
 167 whether the respective elements $A_{i-1} A_{j-1}$ lead to a factorization of
 168 the number D and we set up a table with the respective coincidences
 169 and a column with the values one and zero to designate when the
 170 answer is yes or no for the test.

i	j	fac
1	7	1
2	14	1
3	13	1
4	12	1
5	11	1
6	10	1
7	9	1
9	15	1

172 In this case we observe that all cases lead to a factorization. I con-
 173 jecture that this is an exception that occurs only in cases where the
 174 period of the continued fraction (p) is much smaller than \sqrt{D} .

3.2. Some of the coincidences lead to factorization

175 $D = 2059 = 29 * 71$
 176

i	P_i	Q_i	A_i
-2	-	-	0
-1	-	55	1
0	0	1	45
1	45	-34	91
2	23	45	136
3	22	-35	227
4	13	54	363
5	41	-7	465
6	43	30	1293
7	17	-59	1758
8	42	5	294
9	43	-42	287
10	41	9	818
11	40	-51	1105
12	11	38	1923
13	27	-35	833
14	43	6	1231
15	41	-63	5
16	22	25	1241
17	28	-51	1246
18	23	30	1674
19	37	-23	91
20	32	45	1765
21	13	-42	1856
22	29	29	1359
23	29	-42	1156
24	13	45	456
25	32	-23	465
26	37	30	1386
27	23	-51	1851
28	28	25	970
29	22	-63	762
30	41	6	1343
31	43	-35	1389
32	27	38	673
33	11	-51	3
34	40	9	700
35	41	-42	1403
36	43	5	1902
37	42	-59	1246
38	17	30	276
39	43	-7	440
40	41	54	716
41	13	-35	1156
42	22	45	1872
43	23	-34	782
44	45	1	0

Following the same rule as before, we created the coincidence table:

i	j	fac
1	43	1
2	20	0
3	13	0
4	40	1
5	39	1
6	18	1
7	37	1
8	36	1
9	21	0
10	34	1
11	17	0
12	32	1
13	31	1
14	30	1
15	29	1
16	28	1
17	27	1
18	26	1
19	25	1
20	24	1
21	23	1
23	35	0
24	42	0
26	38	1
27	33	0
31	41	0

180

i	P_i	Q_i	A_i
-2	-	-	0
-1	-	69	1
0	0	1	69
1	69	-98	70
2	29	41	209
3	53	-50	488
4	47	53	1185
5	59	-26	369
6	45	109	1554
7	64	-7	741
8	69	14	3364
9	57	-115	4105
10	58	13	1437
11	59	-106	683
12	47	25	4169
13	53	-82	4852
14	29	49	4155
15	69	-2	7
16	69	49	4169
17	29	-82	4176
18	53	25	1437
19	47	-106	754
20	59	13	3364
21	58	-115	4118
22	57	14	1554
23	69	-7	4490
24	64	109	1185
25	45	-26	4371
26	59	53	209
27	47	-50	4789
28	53	41	69
29	29	-98	4858
30	69	1	0

187

181 Unlike the previous case, we see that out of 26 coincidences 18
 182 resulted in factorization. The period of the expansion was 44 while
 183 $d = \lfloor \sqrt{D} \rfloor = 45$. This reinforces the conjecture that only for cases
 184 where $p \ll d$ will we not have factorization.

i	j	fac
1	29	0
2	28	0
3	27	0
4	26	0
5	25	0
6	24	0
7	23	0
8	22	0
9	21	0
10	20	0
11	19	0
12	18	0
13	17	0
14	16	0

188

189 In this case, none of the coincidences leads to a factorization, which
 190 means that the method does not work in any case. However, we
 191 believe that this is also an exception when, in addition to the condition
 192 of $p \ll d$, there is the condition that the residues are distributed
 193 antisymmetrically in relation to the central element, as we can see in
 194 the tables.

185 **3.3. No factorization**

186 $D = 4859 = 43 * 113$

195 **4. Empirical study of the distribution of coincidences**

196 A fundamental question to be answered in order to configure this
 197 procedure as a factorization method is whether it is possible to deter-
 198 mine the distance between two equal residues. To investigate this, I
 199 constructed a graph with the index of each residue on the abscissa and
 200 the index where this same residue repeats on the ordinate. In future

201 work we will do a detailed analysis of these patterns that emerge in
 202 this graph, and how they can be used as a computational advantage.
 203 Figure ?? shows an example figure.

Figure 1. Mapping of the residue indices for the number 34595515931. The points where factorization occurs are highlighted in red. With a period of 91002 and a total of 75731 repeated elements, of which 57421 lead to factorization.

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204 **5. General Considerations**

205 The main advantage of this procedure is its parallelization. However,
 206 the tests to verify the solution must take into account all the values
 207 already calculated, so a good strategy is necessary to implement this
 208 step. Should a processor be dedicated to performing the tests?

209 How to save the pairs for the tests?

210 Another question to consider is whether there will be values of
 211 $(-1)^i Q_i = (-1)^j Q_j$ for any number D . It is possible to estimate the
 212 order of magnitude of the expansion period in continued fractions of
 213 \sqrt{D} :

$$l(D) \leq \epsilon \log(D)\sqrt{D} + \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{D}) \quad (23)$$

214 where $\epsilon \geq 1$. Since $0 < Q_i < 2\sqrt{D}$ we have that there will necessarily
 215 be repeated values of Q_i , since, for large values of D , $\log(D) > 2$.

216 What, up to now, is not possible to show, is whether these collisions
 217 will be fortuitous and where they will occur. They may be distributed
 218 throughout the entire period or concentrated in some region. This
 219 explains the probabilistic nature of the procedure. If we find an effi-
 220 cient method to find the repeated values of Q_i , the algorithm becomes
 221 deterministic. However, from a mathematical point of view, fortui-
 222 tous collisions may occur with a small number of tests, which makes
 223 any cryptography system that can be broken by integer factorization
 224 potentially vulnerable to this algorithm.

225 **6. Contact me**

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